

ISic0005

Funerary inscription for Marcus Avianus Pistianus, Maria Eupraxia and Marius Eutygianus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3505

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D (is) · M (anibus) · S (acrum) ·
2. M (arcus) · Avianius Pistianus
3. et · Maria Eupraxia vi
4. vi · sibi · et · suis · fece r̄u r̄t
5. et · Mario Eutychiano · fili
6. o suo piissimo · non digno
7. priori qu i vix (it) ann (is) XVII
8. mens (is) · XI dieb (us) XVI

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491502

EDCS 21900325

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7006 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 5

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